

DISTRIBUTED ALGORITHMS FOR ENERGY-EFFICIENT BROADCASTING IN AD HOC NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT

In our earlier work, we developed the Broadcast Incremental Power (BIP) algorithm, which is a centralized heuristic for energy-efficient broadcasting of source-initiated session-based traffic in wireless networks. This algorithm, which exploits the characteristics of the wireless channel, was shown to perform better than adaptations of conventional algorithms that were originally developed for wired networks. However, as a consequence of its centralized nature, it is “expensive” in terms of both communication and computation requirements. In this paper, we develop two distributed versions of BIP, and compare their performance to that of centralized BIP and to an algorithm based on the minimum-cost spanning tree formulation.

I. INTRODUCTION

In our earlier work, we addressed the construction of energy-efficient broadcast trees in wireless networks, and developed the Broadcast Incremental Power (BIP) heuristic [1], [2]. We showed via simulation that BIP provides improvement over “conventional schemes” (i.e., schemes originally designed for wired networks, and which do not exploit the characteristics of the wireless channel).

Although BIP performs well in terms of constructing energy-efficient trees, it is not well suited for use in networks with changing connectivity because it is a centralized algorithm. In this paper, we develop two distributed versions of BIP, we evaluate them by simulation, and we compare their performance to that of centralized BIP. Although the trees produced by the distributed versions are not as energy efficient as those of centralized BIP, the ability to perform all calculations based on local information may justify the additional power cost. We also compare the performance of our distributed schemes to that of the minimum-cost spanning tree (MST), which can be implemented distributedly, e.g., by using the Gallager-Humblet-Spira (GHS) algorithm [3]. We show that, under some reasonable conditions, the performance of the distributed BIP schemes is comparable

to that of MST-based schemes. We also discuss some advantages of distributed BIP that may make it more attractive than MST-based schemes in practice.

A key feature of BIP (in both its centralized and distributed versions) is that RF transmission power (and hence communication range) is chosen as part of the tree-construction process. Thus, energy efficiency is achieved by the joint control of RF power and tree structure. It is often more energy efficient for many of the nodes to transmit at power levels that are well below the maximum permitted p_{max} value. It is assumed that RF power can be controlled continuously so that none is wasted.

The distributed versions of our algorithms use at most “two-hop-away” information to construct trees (where two-hop-away refers to the maximum communication range, at p_{max} , and may correspond to several hops at lower RF power levels). Thus, local tree-construction decisions are based on a much smaller number of nodes (which, in some applications, can be bounded), resulting in greatly reduced communication and computation requirements. These local subtrees are then joined together to form a complete broadcast tree. The amount of communication and computation at any node depends only on its local environment, thus providing scalability as the area covered by the network is increased (while maintaining p_{max} and average node density at roughly constant levels).

BIP [1], [2] was the first energy-efficient broadcasting algorithm to exploit the characteristics of wireless communication channels. Specifically, BIP exploits the broadcast or “node-based” nature of omnidirectional wireless communications [4], which permits all neighboring nodes to receive a transmission. By contrast, most previously developed models for multicasting have been “link-based” models, under which a node must transmit separately to each of its neighbors. Although link-based models are appropriate for wired applications (and to some extent can be adapted to wireless networks [4]), they do not reflect properly the properties of the all-wireless network environment. Furthermore, even though the minimum-cost broadcasting problem is straightforward to solve in wired networks (by formulating it as the MST problem), the corresponding problem in wireless networks has recently been proven to be NP-complete [5], [6].

This work was supported by the Office of Naval Research (ONR) and by the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA).

It was shown in [1] and [2] that, in the vast majority of examples considered, the broadcast trees produced by BIP are more energy efficient than those produced by the link-based MST algorithm.

The broadcast-tree construction problem involves the designation of which nodes are to transmit, and the power levels at which they do so. To assess the complex trade-offs one at a time, we assume in this paper that there is no mobility, even though the handling of mobility is the motivation and the eventual goal of the approach outlined in this paper. In fact, we can already suggest that the impact of mobility can be incorporated into our models because transmitter power can be adjusted to accommodate the new locations of the nodes, as necessary. In other words, the capability to adjust transmission power provides a degree of “elasticity” to the topological connectivity, and hence may reduce the need for hand-offs and tracking. Also, we do not address medium-access control (MAC) issues, although we do address qualitatively the burden placed on the MAC layer by the various algorithms. Therefore, we are able to concentrate on the development of distributed node-based algorithms for wireless networks that are similar in principle to MST algorithms for wired networks, but which exploit the characteristics of the wireless medium.

II. WIRELESS COMMUNICATIONS MODEL

We consider wireless networks in which the node locations are fixed, and the channel conditions unchanging. In addition to interference, another undesirable impact of the use of high transmitter power is that it results in increased energy usage. Since the propagation loss varies nonlinearly with distance, it is typically best to avoid the use of long links. However, since several downstream neighbors may be reached with a single transmission in broadcast applications, it is difficult to make general observations.

The network consists of N nodes, which are randomly distributed over a specified region. The goal is the construction of an energy-efficient broadcast tree, rooted at the source node. The connectivity of the network depends on the transmission power. Following the model of [1], [2], we assume that each node can choose its transmission power level p , such that $p_{min} \leq p \leq p_{max}$. The nodes in a particular multicast tree do not necessarily have to use the same power levels.

We assume that the received signal power is equal to $p^{RF} r^{-\alpha}$, where r is the distance and α is a parameter that typically takes on a value between 2 and 4, depending on the characteristics of the communication medium. Based on this model, the transmitted power required to support a link between two nodes separated by distance r is proportional to r^α , since the received power must exceed

some threshold. Without loss of generality, we set the proportionality constant equal to 1, resulting in:

$$p_{ij}^{RF} = \text{RF power needed for link between Nodes } i \text{ and } j \\ = \max\{r_{ij}^\alpha, p_{min}\}$$

where r_{ij} is the distance between Node i and Node j . The use of a nonzero value of p_{min} is a way to account for the fact that the $r^{-\alpha}$ dependence applies only in the far-field region (i.e., even when two nodes are arbitrarily close to each other, a nonzero power level p_{min} is required to support communication between them).

It is important to note how the broadcast property of omnidirectional wireless communication can be exploited in broadcast and multicast applications. Consider an example in which Node i transmits to its neighbors, Node j and Node k . The RF transmitter power required to reach Node j is p_{ij} and the power required to reach Node k is p_{ik} . A single transmission at power $p_{i,(j,k)} = \max\{p_{ij}, p_{ik}\}$ is sufficient to reach both Node j and Node k , based on our assumption of omnidirectional antennas. We refer to the ability to exploit this property of wireless communication as the “wireless multicast advantage” [4].

III. MINIMUM-ENERGY BROADCAST TREES

We address the problem of constructing the minimum-energy, source-based broadcast tree for each newly arriving broadcast session request. The use of omnidirectional antennas is assumed. Since this problem is NP-complete, it is necessary to develop heuristics. In the specification of a broadcast tree, each transmission by a node is characterized by its transmitter power level, as well as a designation of which (possibly several) of the nodes receiving this transmission are to forward it. In this paper, we address only the energy spent for RF transmission, although energy used for signal processing can be incorporated in a straightforward manner as in [7]. Thus, the total energy of the broadcast tree is simply the sum of the energy expended at each of the transmitting nodes in the tree; leaf nodes (which do not transmit) do not contribute to this quantity. We evaluate performance in terms of the total power required to maintain the tree. We do not address the protocol energy overhead associated with the establishment of the trees. We expect that this energy expenditure would be low in session-based applications because the session duration is expected to be much longer than that of overhead messages. When data traffic is considered, such overhead would likely no longer be negligible in centralized implementations because of the amount of connectivity information that must be exchanged. However, in distributed implementations since only two-hop-away information must be disseminated, it may be possible to maintain communication overhead at acceptable levels.

A. Use of MSTs

In [1], [2] we compared BIP to a conventional link-based scheme, the Broadcast Link-based MST (BLiMST) algorithm. This algorithm is based on the use of the standard MST formulation (as in wired networks) in which a link cost is associated with each pair of nodes (i.e., the power to sustain the link). We have implemented BLiMST in a centralized manner using Prim's algorithm [8]; it can also be implemented distributedly using the Gallager-Humblet-Spira (GHS) algorithm [3]. Since the MST problem is of polynomial complexity, it is scalable. Although the "wireless multicast advantage" is ignored in the construction of the MST, the evaluation of tree cost does take into consideration the wireless multicast advantage; thus, the tree cost is less than the sum of the individual link costs.

IV. THE BIP ALGORITHM

BIP [1], [2] is similar in principle to Prim's algorithm for the formation of MSTs, in the sense that new nodes are added to the tree one at a time (on a minimum-cost basis) until all nodes are included in the tree. However, it differs in that the cost to add a new node is the *incremental* cost, which takes into consideration the power level at which a node is already transmitting.

A. The Sweep: Removing Unnecessary Transmissions

In [1], [2] we noted that the performance of broadcast algorithms can be improved somewhat by using the "sweep" operation, which detects redundant transmissions as well as transmissions that can be reduced in power. The numerical results presented in this paper are based on a version of the sweep in which the entire tree is constructed before searching for opportunities to improve performance. This approach typically provides better performance than an alternative approach in which a sweep is performed at each step during the tree construction. Typically, a single application of the sweep operation provides significant improvement; small further improvement can often be obtained by repeating the sweep once more, but little improvement has been found by additional applications of this procedure.

Although the sweep is a centralized procedure, it is straightforward to collect the information specifying the entire tree structure at a central node, i.e., by sending messages from all leaf nodes back to the Source via the pre-swept tree. Thus, the centralized sweep can be used, even when the tree is constructed by using a distributed algorithm. Nevertheless, it would be helpful to develop a fully distributed sweep algorithm, and this is a topic for future research.

V. INFORMATION AVAILABLE AT THE NODES

BIP is a centralized algorithm. Its execution requires knowledge of the communication cost (in our case RF transmission power¹) between every pair of nodes in the network. It is certainly possible to gather this information at one particular node (e.g., a network controller), provided that network topology, propagation conditions, and interference levels remain fixed. Once the network controller computes the tree, it can broadcast (e.g., by flooding) the tree structure (i.e., set of transmitting nodes, their RF transmitting powers, and downstream neighbors) to all network nodes. Alternatively, if complete information on communication costs is available at all nodes, each node can compute a consistent version of the broadcast tree (rooted at any particular source node) without further exchange of information with its neighbors since BIP uses deterministic rules to construct the tree.

To facilitate our discussion, we introduce some definitions. Two nodes are considered to be "neighbors" as long as the RF power required to connect directly them does not exceed p_{max} ; otherwise, they are not neighbors and the cost to link them directly is ∞ . The "neighborhood" of a node is simply the set of its neighbors. The "two-hop-neighborhood" of a node is the union of the neighborhoods of all neighbors, *excluding* the neighbors themselves. Correspondingly, we define "two-hop-neighbors" to be nodes in the two-hop-neighborhood (again *excluding* the neighbors themselves). In Fig. 1, the neighborhood of the Node i is the circle of radius r_{max} which is the range that corresponds to p_{max} . Node i 's two-hop neighborhood (the union of circular regions of radius r_{max} centered at each of Node i 's neighbors, excluding Node i 's neighborhood) is shown with darker shading.

Fig. 1 – Neighborhood and two-hop-neighborhood.

¹ In general, any model for link (or node) cost can be used with BIP; e.g., the propagation constant α does not have to be uniform throughout the region, and the presence of obstacles may block some links (resulting in a link cost of ∞).

In the distributed algorithms considered in this paper, we assume that the following information (which can be obtained via channel probing) is available at Node i :

- the cost between Node i and each of its neighbors
- the cost between each pair of Node i 's neighbors (set to ∞ if it is greater than p_{max})

In our second scheme, the following additional information is available:

- the cost between each of Node i 's neighbors and their neighbors (that are two-hop neighbors of Node i)

It is important to note that, under either scheme, the following information is NOT available at Node i :

- the cost between Node i 's two-hop neighbors. For example, in Fig. 1, Node i does not know the cost between Node j and Node k .

Thus, Node i knows the communication cost between a pair of nodes if and only if at least one of them is within its neighborhood. If both are two-hop neighbors, then this information is not available

By assuming the information discussed above is available, we effectively neglect MAC-layer issues so we can concentrate on the performance of the distributed algorithms under ideal circumstances. However, we acknowledge that MAC-layer issues are highly nontrivial, and must be addressed eventually.

VI. DISTRIBUTED IMPLEMENTATIONS OF BIP

We now consider two alternative distributed implementations of BIP. We refer to these schemes as Distributed-BIP-All (Dist-BIP-A) and Distributed-BIP-Gateways (Dist-BIP-G). They differ in the choice of nodes selected to take an active role in tree construction. We begin by discussing the features common to both versions. Under both schemes, each node has the information described in the previous section (Dist-BIP-G uses the costs between neighbors and two-hop neighbors, whereas Dist-BIP-A does not). Based on the available information, each node acts as if it were the source node, and constructs (essentially off-line) a broadcast tree by executing BIP using only the information available to it.

A. Distributed-BIP-All (Dist-BIP-A)

Each node computes its local BIP tree, as discussed above. Then, when a broadcast message is generated at a node, that node becomes the Source node, and hence the root of the tree that is to be constructed. It broadcasts its locally generated BIP tree structure to all of its neighbors. The simplest (although not necessarily the most energy-efficient) way to do so is to broadcast the tree structure using RF power sufficient to reach the farthest of its neighbors (which may be less than p_{max}).

When a node hears from a node that is already in the tree, it broadcasts its own locally generated BIP tree to all of its neighbors, using a flooding-like procedure. Thus, the tree expands in all directions simultaneously. This scheme permits nodes to hear from multiple parent nodes. We use a simple temporal rule in such cases, i.e., once a node has heard from a parent, it does not switch to another parent; however, it does acquire downstream nodes based on local trees generated by all upstream nodes that it hears from. Alternatively, it would be possible to develop rules that may involve changing parents, if doing so results in lower tree cost.

An obvious disadvantage of Dist-BIP-A is that, since each node will typically hear from several parents, there is a great deal of overhead. This overhead not only results in wasted energy, but puts an unacceptable load on the MAC layer, possibly resulting in an excessive level of contention for channel access. Therefore, we have considered the following scheme.

B. Distributed-BIP-Gateways (Dist-BIP-G)

The Dist-BIP-G algorithm assumes that additional information is available at Node i , namely the cost between Node i 's neighbors and two-hop neighbors. For example, for the topology of Fig. 1, Node i computes the tree shown in Fig. 2. The tree is based on full information in the neighborhood of Node i , and on partial information in the two-hop neighborhood of Node i . Specifically, links between two-hop neighbors are not included, since Node i does not know that they exist. Consequently, each two-hop neighbor is connected to the tree via a neighbor of Node i . We use the term *gateway* to refer to a neighbor of Node i that connects to one or more of Node i 's two-hop neighbors.

Fig. 2 — A tree based on full information within the Source's neighborhood and partial information outside it.

The links between the gateways and their neighbors are not used in the final version of the global tree. These links are often not energy efficient because they are based on

only partial information; thus, they can't take advantage of the possibility of relaying in the two-hop neighborhood. However, the designation of gateways is useful because the set of gateways forms a sufficient set to reach all of node i 's two-hop neighbors. Therefore, it is sufficient for only the gateway nodes (rather than all nodes) to broadcast their locally generated BIP trees.

The Dist-BIP-G scheme poses a lower burden on the MAC layer than does Dist-BIP-A because fewer nodes (i.e., only the gateways) are contending for channel access. As network density increases, we expect that the fraction of nodes that will be gateways will decrease. Nevertheless, MAC-layer issues remain a significant unresolved issue.

As above, it is still possible for a node to hear from multiple parents, so we use the same temporal rule: once a node hears from a parent it does not change its parent.

C. Implementation Details

Under both Dist-BIP-A and Dist-BIP-G, tree construction proceeds outwards from the source node in all directions simultaneously. Under the former, all nodes broadcast their contribution (subtree) to the overall broadcast tree. Under the latter, only the gateways do so.

We have implemented Dist-BIP-A and Dist-BIP-G on a sequential computer. In doing so, we have made some arbitrary choices as to the order in which tree construction proceeds. Specifically, we use node ID to determine which node is next to add its subtree to the network. At each step, among the candidate nodes for expanding the tree (under Dist-BIP-A, all nodes that are already in the tree, but which have not broadcast their subtrees; under Dist-BIP-G, all gateway nodes that are already in the tree, but which not have broadcast their subtrees), the node with the lowest ID is chosen. Thus, node ID has an impact on the ultimate tree structure (since the temporal rule is used to fix parent nodes), unlike centralized BIP whose trees depend only on communication costs.

Alternative approaches to choosing the order in which construction proceeds are certainly possible. For example, if the goal were to grow the tree at a similar rate in all directions, under Dist-BIP-G it would be possible to require that all first-level gateways (gateways designated by the original source) add their subtrees before proceeding to the gateways' gateways, etc. Node ID might be used to break ties among nodes at the same level, but would not have as great an impact as in the strictly ID-based scheme just discussed.

If a truly distributed implementation were used (in which a node broadcasts its subtree as soon as it hears from a parent, regardless of node ID or distance from the Source), the order of execution would depend in part on how the MAC layer is implemented, including collision-resolution issues.

VII. PERFORMANCE RESULTS

We have evaluated the performance of our algorithms for many network examples. For each set of parameters, 100 networks, each with 1000 nodes, are randomly generated within a square region (e.g., 5×5), i.e., the location of each node is randomly generated. One of the nodes is randomly chosen to be the Source. We assume a propagation loss exponent of $\alpha = 2$; thus RF transmitter power is r^2 .

Table 1 summarizes the average performance (i.e., average tree power) of four algorithms, namely centralized BIP, MST, Dist-BIP-A, and Dist-BIP-G, where the average is taken over the 100 network instances. Results are shown for $p_{max} = 0.2, 0.5, \text{ and } 1$. We provide results both with and without the sweep operation.

Table 1 — Average tree power.

	$p_{max} = 0.2$	$p_{max} = 0.5$	$p_{max} = 1$
	Without Sweep		
BIP	10.642	10.642	10.642
MST	11.345	11.345	11.345
Dist-BIP-A	14.076	12.787	12.090
Dist-BIP-G	15.555	15.225	14.047
	With Sweep		
BIP	10.069	10.069	10.069
MST	10.793	10.793	10.793
Dist-BIP-A	11.833	11.222	10.848
Dist-BIP-G	11.972	11.480	11.003

The use of $p_{max} = 0.2$ is sufficient to provide a connected network, and the results for centralized BIP and MST do not change when p_{max} is increased. However, the performance of the Dist-BIP schemes improves as p_{max} increases. The poor performance of the Dist-BIP schemes for low values of p_{max} can be attributed to the fact that Dist-BIP approaches flooding when the diameter of the locally generated trees is small. As p_{max} increases, the local trees develop more of a multihop structure, so the benefits of applying BIP locally become more apparent. Even at the highest value of RF power we have considered ($p_{max} = 1$), a significant number of local trees are connected to create the global tree; thus we do see the effects of distributed operation.

It is clear from Table 1 that centralized BIP provides the best average performance in all cases. Moreover, centralized BIP actually provides the lowest value of tree power in each of the 100 network instances for each case that has been considered. The ranking of the other three algorithms (from best to worst) is: MST, Dist-BIP-A, Dist-BIP-G. When $p_{max} = 1$ and the sweep is used, the average

power associated with Dist-BIP-A is only 0.5% greater than that of MST. Therefore, it would be worthwhile to investigate implementation issues (e.g, at the MAC layer) to see if there are compelling reasons to prefer one of these approaches to the other.

We believe that the relatively poor performance of Dist-BIP-G results from its incorporation of two-hop neighbors into the local tree, based on only partial information. The inclusion of these nodes can result in energy inefficiencies in Node i 's neighborhood. We are currently considering an alternative implementation of Dist-BIP-G, in which two-hop neighbors (which are needed to determine the gateways) are not added to the local tree until all neighbors have been added. Thus, each node would first compute its local tree with the same database that is available to Dist-BIP-A. Once this is done, it would add to its database the costs between its neighbors and two-hop neighbors, and continue to construct its local tree. However, links between neighbors and two-hop neighbors are not retained in the local tree; they are used only to determine which nodes should be gateways.

A. Dist-BIP vs MST

The results of the previous subsection suggest that use of MST-based schemes may be more appropriate than Dist-BIP, since they provide slightly better performance and have lower complexity. However, we feel that Dist-BIP may have some advantages that are not fully apparent from the discussion thus far.

MST can be implemented using the distributed GHS algorithm, which has both synchronous and asynchronous versions [9]. Under these schemes, disjoint subtrees are grown simultaneously, and merged to produce the final tree. However, a possible disadvantage of these schemes (or other distributed implementations of MST) is that knowledge of the entire subtree constructed thus far must be maintained by at least one node in each such subtree, thus necessitating the storage of information regarding many-hop-away nodes. Even though memory requirements to do so will not be excessive, another issue must be addressed. Namely, topological changes many hops away can change the local decisions of nodes as they compute their contribution to the tree. By contrast, the Dist-BIP schemes may be potentially more robust to such topological changes because decisions are based on only neighboring nodes. Another potential advantage of the more-localized nature of Dist-BIP is that it may be suitable for packet-oriented systems because it would be possible to begin the broadcast before the entire tree is constructed. Future research is needed to gain a better understanding of issues such as these.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have developed and evaluated distributed versions of the BIP algorithm for energy-efficient broadcasting in wireless networks. Although they do not perform as well as centralized BIP, the ability to construct trees distributedly is important because centralized algorithms are impractical in extremely large or highly mobile networks. Although the distributed BIP schemes do not perform as well as the conventional MST formulation, they perform sufficiently well to warrant investigation of implementation issues, especially when the value of p_{max} is relatively large.

For example, further research is needed to assess the MAC-layer issues associated with all of the algorithms considered in this paper. These issues are critical and not well understood, not only in environments characterized by changing topology, but even in static environments. Questions to be addressed include not only tree power, but also communication and computational complexity, as well as robustness to topological change.

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